

Particle Swarm Optimization Based Feature Selection on Diagnostic of Lung Cancer Disease

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Abstract

Cancer is the disease that occurs when cells in any organ or tissue are divided and multiplied in an irregular manner. This disease which is one of the most important health problems of today can be treated successfully with various techniques that have emerged in recent years. Diagnosis of cancer diseases with the help of numerical data obtained from microarray data sets requires a lot of processing power due to the high dimensionality of the data sets. In this study; The data set for lung cancer was reduced with Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) methods and classified with k-Nearest Neighbor (k-NN) and Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO) algorithms. Classification results obtained after the size reduction process are compared with various performance analysis data.

1 INTRODUCTION

According to the earliest known sources, cancer dating back centuries to the present-day dates back to about 3000 BC. The word cancer is derived from the Latin word "canker" or "carcinus", which means crab [1]. The emergence of cancer has increased the mortality rate from the disease. Today, there is a certain amount of cancer deaths every year. One of the most important reasons for this is the inadequate diagnosis of cancer or late diagnosis. However, as a result of scientific research and studies carried out with the development of technology, the rate of cancer detection increases. In this way, early diagnosis, which is one of the most important factors to know for cancer, has produced more successful results. According to a study conducted in the United States between 2007 and 2013, lung cancer ranked 6th among cancer types with a survival rate of 18.1% [2]. As shown in Figure 1, the mortality rate from cancer in Turkey constitutes approximately 20% of all deaths [3].

Figure 1. Cancer Mortality Rates per year in Turkey

Cancerous diseases, which have not even been treated before, have now been successfully improved for both treatment and detection. In addition to the methods used for the treatment and detection of cancer diseases, new methods have been developed with the development of technology. The optimization algorithms developed through innovations in technology and research are performed classification and performance analysis in cancer

detection [4]. The DNA microarray consists of a high-density gene sequence that enables expression analysis of thousands of genes [5]. DNA microarray data analysis plays an important role, particularly in identifying genes associated with diseases such as cancer [6]. The probability of a healthy or sick analysis is calculated by identifying the genes associated with cancer. Therefore, size reduction techniques and high-performance classification methods are used for the analysis of large-scale data such as microarray data sets [7].

In this study, the effect of Particle Swarm Optimization based feature selection on the diagnosis of Lung cancer disease problem was observed. For this purpose, various performance criteria have been compared as a result of the classification of data sets obtained from heuristic and non-heuristic feature selection methods.

2 MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Dataset

In this study, microarray dataset which was produced by Bhattacharjee et al., in 2001 to diagnose lung cancer disease was used [8]. This data set contains 12600 gene information from 4 different lung tumors and healthy individuals from 203 subjects. Class information for the data set is as follows;

Diagnostic classes:

- Adenocarcinoma (AD): 139 samples (68.5%)
- Normal lung (NL): 17 samples (8.4%)
- Small cell lung cancer (SMCL): 6 samples (3.0%)
- Squamous cell carcinoma (SQ): 21 samples (10.3%)
- Pulmonary carcinoid (COID): 20 samples (9.9%)

2.2 Feature Selection

The feature selection: to determine the number of variables that are “significant”, to guide and halt the search for good variable subsets, to choose hyperparameters, and to evaluate the final performance of the system [9]. In this subsection, we describe the feature selection methods we used in this study.

2.2.1 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Karl Pearson's principal components analysis (PCA), which was initiated in 1901, was developed by Hotelling in 1933. It is a statistical method used to reduce the number of attributes used as a machine learning technique [10]. It is used to accelerate the learning process.

PCA allows to find the maximum variance values in large-sized data and project them into a new subspace location that is equal to or less than the original data. Therefore, it is desirable that the variance of the new subspace be maximum and its size to be minimum.

Working steps of PCA method [11];

- Step 1: Import the entire data set,
- Step 2: Calculate the average values of all dimensions,
- Step 3: Calculate the distribution matrix (covariance matrix) of the whole data set,
- Step 4: Calculate the eigenvectors (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_d) and the corresponding eigenvalues ($\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_d$),
- Step 5: Select the eigenvalue k with the largest eigenvalue to generate the $d \times k$ matrix W (where each column represents an eigenvector) by sorting the eigenvalues in the resulting table from lower to larger,
- Step 6: Convert the samples onto the new subspace using the resulting $d \times k$ eigenvector matrix. $y = WT \times x$ (x is a $d \times 1$ dimensional vector representing an instance and y is a $k \times 1$ dimensional sample transformed in the new subspace).

2.2.2 Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO)

PSO is an optimization technique developed by Eberhart and Kennedy in 1995, inspired by birds, fish, and insects acting in flock form. The basis of this algorithm is based on herd intelligence. With the help of this optimization, some situations such as food and safety can be realized more easily thanks to the fact that animals moving in flock often exhibit random movements. Communication between individuals is based on social information sharing. The search is performed according to the generation number as in genetic algorithms. Each individual used in optimization is called a particle and the population of these particles is called a herd. These

particles are considered an agent and each agent offer a solution. Each particle is set to its own position as the best position in the flock, taking advantage of the previous experience. The PSO is based on the process of bringing the positions of individuals whose main purpose is in the herd closer to the individual in the best-determined position of the herd. The speed of this approach is a random occurrence, and the new movement positions of the individuals in the herd are often improved to a better position than the previous one and this process continues continuously until it reaches the target [12].

The working steps of the PSO method [13];

Step 1: A start sequence is generated with a randomly generated start position and speeds,

Step 2: Compliance values of all particles in the generated flock are calculated,

Step 3: Local best (pbest) values are available for each particle from the current generation. The best in the flock is the number of particles,

Step 4: Global best (local) is selected among the local best.

In this study, an equal number of attributes were selected for both methods in order to reveal the difference between PSO and PCA. The selected attributes were trained with a back propagation artificial neural network and the mean absolute error value was calculated. While training the artificial neural network, 70% of the data set was determined as training, 15% as validation and 15% as a test set. The best features to minimize the mean absolute error value obtained were determined for 20 iterations and 50 populations.

2.3 Classification

The task of the classifier component proper of a full system is to use the feature vector provided by the feature extractor to assign the object to a category. Because perfect classification performance is often impossible, a more general task is to determine the probability for each of the possible categories. The abstraction provided by the feature-vector representation of the input data enables the development of a largely domain-independent theory of classification [14]. In this subsection, the classification algorithms we used in this study are explained.

2.3.1 Sequential Minimal Optimization (SMO)

The SMO, developed by John Platt in 1998, is an optimization algorithm used to solve quadratic programming problems that arise during SVM training, a very powerful and versatile machine learning model [15]. The LibSVM algorithm used by the algorithm used for studies, SVM has been the focus of interest by the community and has been found to be less complex and cost-effective than previously used methods [16], [17].

2.3.2 k-Nearest Neighbor Algorithm (k-NN)

The k-NN uses non-parametric methods for classification and regression analysis. The input part of these operations consists of training data samples closest to the value of the "k" parameter in the attribute space [18]. In this classification algorithm, a sample classified by its neighbors by majority vote is assigned from the nearest neighbors to the most common situation around it. The fact that the value of this "k" parameter is a positive, odd and small number is ideal for solving general problems, but this may vary according to certain problems. If "k = 1" is selected, the object is assigned to the first state class that is closest to it.

2.4 Performance Criteria

2.4.1 Cross-Validation (CV)

The CV is the technique used to train an algorithm and evaluate the statistical performance of the same data. In the data set used, it separates "n" sets containing data states of equal values and works as the process of using "n-1" of these sets for the training stage and the remaining set for the testing stage. This avoids the problem of testing on the data used for the training phase. In addition, by repeating this operation "n" times, all data is classified. The averages of the "n" grain performance analysis values generated at the end of each process show the average values of the whole process [19]. Generally, n = "2,5,10,20" are commonly used. For this study, "n = 10" was chosen.

2.4.2 Accuracy

Accuracy means that the estimation results resulting from a classification process indicate the proximity to the actual results. The high result of the classification is positive but is not a sufficient performance criterion alone. This has a great effect especially on the distribution of data [20].

2.4.3 Kappa

The Kappa coefficient is a statistical method that measures the reliability of the comparative agreement between two evaluators (observer) in the evaluation of categorical items [21]. The Kappa coefficient is a coefficient in the range -1 to +1 with random value of 0. However, such a coefficient is of little use in practice, without clear meaning and interpretation. As a result, a common use was created between unclassified kappa, " k_i ", which measures the understanding (reliability) of multiple independent measures of the unordered categorical structure, and the weighted kappa, " k_w ", which measures the correlation or relationship between two unordered categorical structures [22].

2.4.4 Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC)

The MCC which is introduced by Brian W. Matthews in 1975 is a method using for the measure of the quality of binary (two-class) classifications [23]. It takes into account true and false positives and negatives and is generally regarded as a balanced measure which can be used even if the classes are of very different sizes [24]. The MCC is a correlation coefficient between the observed and predicted binary classifications; it returns a value between -1 and +1. A coefficient of +1 represents a perfect prediction, 0 no better than random prediction and -1 indicates total disagreement between prediction and observation.

2.4.5 Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC)

The ROC methodology was developed in the early 1950s for the analysis of signal detection. The ROC curve is determined by the ratio of accuracy to accuracy in classification systems for each value of the measurement or model. This definition can be briefly described as the ratio of the value of true positives to the value of false positives. This process is also known as the Relative Operating Characteristic because it compares the two process characteristics [25].

3 RESULTS

In Table 1 and Table 2, the performance values obtained as a result of the classification of 12600 features of the lung cancer disease data set and 106 features obtained after size reduction are given. Classification procedures were performed with the help of the Euclidean distance function and k-NN algorithm with $k = 5$ neighborhood parameter and SMO algorithm with a polynomial kernel. In order to perform performance analysis in size reduction algorithms, the number of attributes was kept equal. (F: Refers to the number of attributes included in the data set).

10-Fold CV, k = 5				
Methods	<i>Accuracy %</i>	<i>Kappa</i>	<i>MCC</i>	<i>ROC</i>
None <i>F: 12600</i>	89.6552	0.7695	0.679	0.942
PCA <i>F: 106</i>	67.4877	0.2751	0.1702	0.803
PSO <i>F: 106</i>	90.6404	0.7928	0.679	0.94

As can be seen in Table 1, the results obtained by the classification of the data set with 12600 attributes are lower than the classification after size reduction. This shows that attribute selection algorithms not only reduce computational complexity but also affect classification results positively. However, it is seen that the PCA

algorithm, which is one of the traditional feature reduction methods, fails against the heuristic optimization algorithm.

Table 2. SMO Classification Results

10-Fold CV				
Methods	Accuracy %	Kappa	MCC	ROC
None <i>F: 12600</i>	95,5665	0,9091	0,904	0,955
PCA <i>F: 106</i>	92,6108	0,8487	0,839	0,921
PSO <i>F: 106</i>	96,0591	0,9187	0,915	0,952

As shown in Table 2, the classification results obtained after PSO-assisted size reduction were higher than all the results, as in the previous step. This demonstrates the efficiency of the feature selection process with the help of optimization algorithms in high dimensional data sets. However, when the classification algorithms used are compared, it is seen that SMO classifier produces more efficient results than k-NN classifier. This demonstrates the success of the kernel function is parsing data sets.

4 CONCLUSION

In this study, lung data set was reduced with the help of PSO and PCA size reduction algorithms and classified with the help of k-NN and SMO algorithms. When the results obtained from both classifiers are examined, it is seen that the feature selection process performed with PSO produces higher results than both PCA and raw data set. This is directly in line with the principle of size reduction algorithms that "the increase in classification results occurs as the number of attributes decreases". Also, this suggests that optimization algorithms work very efficiently in multidimensional data sets. In addition, it is seen that SMO algorithm is more successful in parsing data than k-NN algorithm. All results obtained represent the average of the 10-fold cross-validation method.

In our future studies, we plan to examine the effects of different heuristic optimization algorithms in the diagnosis of cancer diseases.

References

- [1] O. Baykara, "Kanser Tedavisinde Güncel Yaklaşımlar," *Balıkesir Sağlık Bilim. Derg.*, 2017.
- [2] National Cancer Institute, "Browse the SEER Cancer Statistics Review (CSR) 1975-2014." [Online]. Available: https://seer.cancer.gov/archive/csr/1975_2014/browse_csr.php?sectionSEL=1&pageSEL=sect_01_table.05.html. [Accessed: 18-Jul-2019].
- [3] TÜİK, "Ölüm Nedeni İstatistikleri," 2015. [Online]. Available: http://www.tuik.gov.tr/PreTablo.do?alt_id=1083. [Accessed: 10-Jul-2019].
- [4] H. Liu, I. Bebu, and X. Li, "Microarray probes and probe sets.," *Front. Biosci. (Elite Ed)*., 2010.
- [5] H. U. Luleyap, *The Principles of Molecular Genetics*. İzmir: Nobel Yayınevi, 2008.
- [6] K. İpekdal, "Microarray Technology," 2019. [Online]. Available: http://yunus.hacettepe.edu.tr/~mergen/sunu/s_mikroarrayandecology.pdf. [Accessed: 10-Jul-2019].
- [7] M. Hall and L. Smith, "Practical feature subset selection for machine learning," in *21st Australasian computer science conference*, 1998.
- [8] A. Bhattacharjee *et al.*, "Classification of human lung carcinomas by mRNA expression profiling reveals distinct adenocarcinoma subclasses," *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.*, 2001.
- [9] "An introduction to variable and feature selection," *J. Mach. Learn. Res. - JMLR*, 2003.

- [10] I. T. Joliffe and B. Morgan, "Principal component analysis and exploratory factor analysis," *Stat. Methods Med. Res.*, 1992.
- [11] S. Kiliçarslan, A. Kemal, and O. Cömert, "Parçacık Sürü Optimizasyonu Kullanılarak Boyutu Azaltılmış Mikrodizi Verileri Üzerinde Makine Öğrenmesi Yöntemleri ile Prostat Kanseri Teşhisi," *Düzce Üniversitesi Bilim ve Teknoloji Derg.*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 769–777.
- [12] J. Kennedy and R. Eberhart, "Particle Swarm Optimization," in *Neural Networks Proceedings., IEEE International Conference*, 1995.
- [13] M. Y. Özsağlam and M. Çunkaş, "Optimizasyon problemlerinin çözümü için parçacık sürü optimizasyonu algoritması," *Politek. Derg.*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 299–305, 2008.
- [14] R. O. Duda, P. E. Hart, and D. G. Stork, "Pattern Classification (2nd ed.)," *Comput. Complex.*, 1998.
- [15] J. Platt, "Sequential Minimal Optimization: A Fast Algorithm for Training Support Vector Machines," *URL citeeet. ist. psu. edu/platt98sequential. html*, 1998.
- [16] R. M. Rifkin, "Everything old is new again: a fresh look at historical approaches in machine learning," *MaSSachuSettS InStitute of Technology*, 2002.
- [17] L. Zanni, T. Serafini, and G. Zanghirati, "Parallel software for training large scale support vector machines on multiprocessor systems," *J. Mach. Learn. Res.*, vol. 7, no. Jul, pp. 1467–1492, 2006.
- [18] N. S. Altman, "An introduction to kernel and nearest-neighbor nonparametric regression," *Am. Stat.*, 1992.
- [19] R. Kohavi, "A study of cross-validation and bootstrap for accuracy estimation and model selection," *Proc. 14th Int. Jt. Conf. Artif. Intell. - Vol. 2*, 1995.
- [20] E. R. Cohen, "An introduction to error analysis: The study of uncertainties in physical measurements." IOP Publishing, 1998.
- [21] J. Cohen, "A coefficient of agreement for nominal scales. Educational and Psychological Measurement," *Educ. Psychol. Meas.*, 1960.
- [22] H. C. Kraemer, "Kappa coefficient," *Wiley StatsRef Stat. Ref. Online*, pp. 1–4, 2014.
- [23] B. W. Matthews, "Comparison of the predicted and observed secondary structure of T4 phage lysozyme," *BBA - Protein Struct.*, 1975.
- [24] S. Boughorbel, F. Jarray, and M. El-Anbari, "Optimal classifier for imbalanced data using Matthews Correlation Coefficient metric," *PLoS One*, 2017.
- [25] J. A. Swets, *Signal detection theory and ROC analysis in psychology and diagnostics: Collected papers*. Psychology Press, 2014.